

SEISMIC SEQUENCE ARCHITECTURE AND STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS OF NORTHEASTERN NIGERIA CHAD (BORNU) BASIN

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ABSTRACT

An elucidation of the seismic sequence architecture and assessment of the various structural trapping features common in Northeastern Nigeria Chad Basin were carried out in this study. The Chad Basin has proven petroleum reserves in sectors of other bounding countries and not same in the Nigerian sector of it. The analysis and interpretation of the data set comprising seismic reflection time sections and well logs encompassed seismic stratigraphy, structural and log-sequence stratigraphy. This was aimed at establishing the sequence architecture and trapping mechanisms in relation to the petroleum potential of this sector of the basin. The stratigraphic succession of the Bornu Basin is sub-divisible into two genetic units that are separated by type 1 sequence boundaries. Sequence unit 1 overlies the crystalline rocks unconformably, while sequence unit 11 extends thereof to the earth's surface. Petroleum traps includes unconformity trap, lateral facies change towards structural highs, high angle normal and reverse faults, grabens, horst, and symmetrical folds. The main normal fault blocks resulted from extensional stress directed away from the main axis of the Benue Trough – Chad Basin. The fault planes and fault related features are steeply dipping which are common with rifted basins dominated by extensional stress. Consequently, they may not be sealing to petroleum migration because they could be open fractures especially at shallow depths. This makes faults associated traps in this sector of the basin to be less attractive because of high risks of drilling dry holes. The folds appear to be related to randomly distributed magmatic intrusives that underthrust the basal sequence strata and consequently their folding into structural highs. Folding is localized and of no definite pattern and hence may not be due to regional compressional stress. The igneous intrusives could have degradational effects on petroleum pools if it occurred post-migration. The unconformity surface could act as a conduit for petroleum migration and probably dispersal.

KEYWORDS: Sequence stratigraphy, extensional stress, normal faults, folds and igneous intrusives.

INTRODUCTION

The Chad basin is an intra-continental rifted basin, which extends from Northeastern Nigeria to Chad Republic, Niger Republic and the Cameroon within latitudes 10°N to 14°N and longitudes 12°E to 15°E (Figure 1). It is believed to be genetically related to the Benue Trough, which resulted from a failed arm of a triple junction when South American continent separated from the African continent in Early Cretaceous. These two basins are however, separated by the Zambuk Ridge (Burke, (1969), and Genik (1992). Since the late 70s, the Nigerian sector of the basin has been an area of interest in terms of hydrocarbon exploration mainly by the Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation (NNPC). Early exploration works were by Shell-D Arcy in 1938, and later Mobil Exploration Nigeria Limited in 1955. At about 1965, all the oil prospecting companies limited their activities to the Southern Nigeria sedimentary basins, especially the Niger Delta.

The Nigerian sector of the Chad basin (Bornu basin) has been adjudged to possess some favourable critical criteria for high petroleum prospect. These include: age of the basin (Burke, 1969), thickness of the sequence (Rayment 1965, Matheis, 1976, Petters, 1981, and Okosun 1995), source rock geochemistry (Petters and Ekweozor (1982), potential traps (Agagu and Ekweozor, (1980), and Avbovbo *et al.*, (1986), reservoir rocks (Avbovbo *et al.*, (1986), and Okosun, (1995), and a comparative geothermal gradient (Albrecht and Ourisson, (1969), and Ekweozor and Okoye, 1980). However, intensive seismic investigation and drilling of several exploratory wells for over two decades by the Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation has yielded no fruitful result. Moreover, the Federal Government of Nigeria seems not convinced that the basin could be barren, since commercial quantity of petroleum had been reportedly discovered in the Chad and Niger Republics that commonly share the basin. Imperatively, an understanding of its sequence architecture and structural framework is needed so as to elucidate its petroleum trapping mechanisms and effects of reported magmatic intrusives on its petroleum potentials. Tensional stress is commonly dominant over compressional stress in rifted basins. This commonly produces steeply dipping fault

planes and fault related features that may not be sealing to petroleum migration. The structural folding of the sedimentary sequence if due to magmatic intrusives can lead to degradation or cracking existing petroleum pools.

This understanding will immensely aid in a better assessment of its petroleum prospect. Moreover, this can be used for correlation with neighbouring producing fields of Chad and Niger Republics to establish continuity conditions in the entire basin.

Though the direct application of concepts of seismic sequence stratigraphy to lacustrine environments is still being developed, Liro (1994), has applied these concepts in delineating seismic sequences, system tracts and parasequences in the Paleocene Upper Fort Union

Fig. 1: Map of Nigeria showing the location of Chad (Bornu) Basin, inset is a map of Africa showing the location of Nigeria

Fig. 2: Location map of the study area with some seismic lines indicated therein.

Formation. This is a fluvial-deltaic-lacustrine system strongly influenced by tectonic uplift and related subsidence associated with the Late Cretaceous-Early Tertiary Laramide Orogeny of Western North America. This work adopts an integrated study of seismic reflection data and well logs acquired in the Bornu basin to deduce its seismic sequence architecture and structural framework. This is aimed at elucidating its petroleum trapping mechanisms and evaluation of their capabilities to retain petroleum into pools.

Geology of the Chad Basin

The Chad basin is situated in N.E Nigeria and extends to Niger, Chad and Cameroon Republics. Petters (1981), described the Chad basin as an epirogenic downwarp basin whose formation was initiated in the upper Cretaceous. It occasionally opened to the sea and dominated by shallow marine condition. Sedimentation conditions ranged from marine, estuarine, deltaic, to continental that resulted in a stratigraphic sequence that has been subdivided into six formations, (Matheis, (1976), Petters, (1981), and Okosun (1995) as indicated in Table 1.

Table 1: The Stratigraphy of the Chad Basin, modified after Matheis (1976)

Formation	Lithology	Depositional Environment	Age
Chad Formation	Sandy Strata interlayered by argillaceous sediments	Fluvial, and mixed environment	Pleistocene to Pliocene
Keri-Keri Formation	Grit, sandstone and clayey grit	Fluvial, lacustrine	Paleocene
Gombe sandstone	Sandstone with intercalation of shale, siltstone and ironstone	Estuarine to Deltaic	Maestrichtian
Filka shale	Shale	Center lacustrine and marine	Senonian
Gongilia Formation	Mixed limestone/shale sequence	Marginal to center lacustrine and marine	Turonian
Bima Sandstone		Continental	Cenomanian
Basement complex			Pre-Cenomanian

The Bima sandstone overlies the basement rocks unconformably. There was an intense folding of the Cretaceous formations at the end of the Cretaceous leading to the formation of several anticlinal features and erosional activities partly wearing away the upper Cretaceous strata thereby creating an unconformity surface. The Keri-Keri Formation overlies unconformably this surface while the Chad Formation overlies it to the earth's surface.

METHODOLOGY

The data set consisting of seismic reflection data and well logs were acquired by the Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation (NNPC) centered in Doili area of the Bornu Basin (Figure 2). The migrated seismic sections have a record length of six seconds while the log types comprise Calipar (Cal), Spontaneous Potential (SP), Gamma ray, (GR), Resistivity/Induction (R_{xo} , R_s and R_l), Sonic (BCSL), Density (FDC) and Neutron (N) logs respectively. The seismic time sections were analyzed into seismic facies units using reflection termination patterns and configurations. Structural interpretation involved the sub-division of the seismic sections into seismic horizons with the fault planes clearly traced on them. Major reflectors were picked within a time range of 0.25s to 2.5s, beyond which there were no major reflectors. Two-way traveltimes to each seismic horizon were used to convert the seismic facies units/horizons from time to depth domain using Dix (1955) equation in a layered cake model. Dix (1955), derived an equation for computing interval velocities (V_i) from root-mean-square velocity (V_r) derivable from velocity spectral analysis during data processing. This equation is expressed as

$$V_{I,n} = \left(\frac{V_{r,n}^2 T_n - V_{r,n-1}^2 T_{n-1}}{T_n - T_{n-1}} \right)^{1/2} \quad (1)$$

Where $V_{I,n}$, is the interval velocity between n^{th} and $(n - 1)^{th}$ reflectors.

$V_{r,n}$, $V_{r,n-1}$ are the rms velocities of the n^{th} , $(n - 1)^{th}$ reflectors, and T_n , and T_{n-1} are the zero offset times for n^{th} and $(n-1)^{th}$ reflectors.

Errors associated with estimation of the root mean square velocity (V_r) were computed using Hajnal and Sereda (1981) simplified equation expressed as

$$\Delta V_{r,n} = \frac{2T_{n-1}}{a} \Delta V_{r,N-1} \quad (2)$$

Where $\Delta V_{r,n}$, $\Delta V_{r,N-1}$ are the errors involved in estimating the V_r of n^{th} and $(n - 1)^{th}$ reflectors.

T_{n-1} is the two-way traveltime to $(n-1)^{th}$ reflector and a is the time thickness of the horizon.

The normalization is necessary because Dix (1955) equation is based on an assumption that the strata/beds are horizontal or angle of dip is insignificant. In situations where there are significant departures from horizontal geometry of reflectors, the stacking velocity (V_s) no longer approximates rms velocity (Taner *et al.*, (1970) and Al – Chalabi, (1974). The stacking velocity is based on the equation expressed as (Telford *et al.*, 1976):

$$T^2 = T_o^2 + \frac{X^2}{V_s^2} \quad (3)$$

Where T is the two-way traveltime to the reflector. T_o is the two-way traveltime at zero offset, X is the offset distance and V_s is the stacking velocity.

The normalized V_r were used for the computation of interval velocities of each seismic horizon that were subsequently used to compute the thickness and depths of the seismic horizons. This enables the visualization of deformation processes in depth domain. Lateral variation of the interval velocities was investigated especially around and within the major folds seen on some of the seismic time sections. Log sequence analysis was carried to deduce the lithostratigraphic sequence, reservoirs' facies, compute petrophysical parameters and evaluating petroleum potentials of reservoirs' facies.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Seismic Sequence Stratigraphy

Two sequence units that are separated type 1 sequence boundaries are delineable on the seismic time sections. The basal sequence boundary separate the stratigraphic succession from the underlying crystalline rocks while the upper sequence boundary separates the structurally deformed lower strata from the overlying relatively undeformed strata. The basal sequence unit is sub-divisible into four seismic facies units / horizons, while the upper sequence unit is sub-divisible into two seismic facies units / horizons. Figures 3 and 4 are interpreted seismic time sections of lines S– 32 and D – 75. Seismic facies unit 1 or horizon 1 overlies the crystalline rocks unconformably. It exhibits sub-parallel to divergent, poorly continuous and moderate amplitude reflections thus indicating fair uniformity of depositional conditions. It is the most affected by basin tectonics with several faults, and reflections terminating at the flanks of intrusive bodies. It exhibit concordant relationship with overlying seismic facies unit, however, the nature of its baselap cannot be determined apparently due to amplitude decay with increasing traveltime. The associated divergent reflection configuration is ascribed to differential subsidence during sedimentation and in places where subsidence is uniform, a sub-parallel reflection configuration results. The sedimentation conditions is inferred that of marginal lacustrine or shallow marine environment.

Seismic facies unit 2 exhibits sub-parallel to parallel reflection configuration, however, continuity of reflections has been truncated by faulting and folding. It exhibits concordant relationship with both overlying and underlying seismic facies units. Moderate depositional energy dominated the environment that is inferred a shallow water facies. Seismic facies unit 3 exhibits mainly sub-parallel to parallel to and continuous reflection configuration except where disrupted by faults and igneous intrusives. Its relationship with facies units below and above is concordant. Its sedimentation conditions are quite similar to that of the underlying seismic facies

Fig. 3: An interpreted seismic section of Line S-32 showing the seismic facies units / horizons and a graben in Northeastern Nigeria Chad (Bornu) Basin.

Fig. 4: An interpreted seismic section of Line D-75 showing the seismic facies units / horizons and an igneous intrusive in Northeastern Nigeria Chad (Bornu) Basin.

units. Seismic facies unit 4 exhibits mainly continuous parallel reflection configuration and concordant relationship with underlying seismic facies unit, however, its relationship with overlying horizon vary from concordant to discordant somehow toplap where a regional unconformity plane separates it from the overlying horizons. Seismic facies unit 5 exhibits mainly parallel, continuous, low to moderate amplitude reflections and a thickening trend in N.E direction (that is, to the present day Lake Chad). It terminates discordantly with underlying regional unconformity plane and concordantly with overlying seismic facies unit. Its sedimentation occurred in a depositional setting sloping gently in the N.E direction dominated by moderate energy. It is unaffected by faulting and folding. Seismic facies unit 6 also exhibits continuous, parallel reflection configuration. It exhibits a concordant relationship with underlying seismic horizon and unaffected by faulting and folding. All the seismic facies units do not exhibit onlapping reflection termination pattern with the igneous intrusives / folds. This implies that they are post-depositional features. The change in base level that accompanied the magmatic intrusives is indicated by the upper sequence boundary.

Figure 5 is a schematic illustration of the seismic sequence architecture of the Northeastern Nigeria Chad Basin. Figure 6 is a structural time map of seismic horizon four. The lithofacies of each seismic facies is not inferred or indicated because more lithologic information from a good number of oil wells, core samples and palaeontological data are needed for high confidence deduction. However, based on existing literature, sedimentary formations above the regional unconformity plane have been assigned Tertiary and Quaternary ages respectively (Rayment (1965), Matheis, (1976), Genik, (1992) and Okosun, (1995). Okosun (1995), asserted that they conform with the Keri-Keri and Chad Formations respectively. The seismic facies units below the unconformity plane have been generally assigned Cretaceous age and no attempt was made in this study to establish their equivalence with the known lithostratigraphic sub-divisions of the Chad Basin. Based on existing literature, these strata have been sub-divided into four formations as listed in Table 1 (Rayment, (1965), Matheis, (1976) and Genik, (1992). Deduced lithologic sequence from lithologic logs indicates two main lithologies – sandstone and shale that are interbedded with gradational lithologies of shaly sand and sandy shale.

Structural Elements

The structural elements are broadly classified into two categories: (a) faults and fault related features and (b) folds. The fault related features in this sector of the basin have arisen from two main causes viz: those due to tensional stress which include normal faults and grabens and those due to underthrusting magmatic intrusives, which includes reverse faults and horsts that are closely associated with the symmetrical folds. Normal faults that resulted from the pull

Fig. 5: Schematic illustration of seismic sequence architecture and structural styles in Northeastern Nigeria Chad (Bornu) Basin.

Fig. 6: Structural depth map of seismic horizon 4 in Northeastern Nigeria Chad (Bornu) Basin.

apart (tensional stress) in northwest and southeast directions and perpendicular to the main axis of Benue Trough-Chad basin (Northeast – Southwest) are more abundant than reverse faults. In places where displacement is uniform on adjacent fault planes, a major graben result. Subordinate normal faults that cut across the major fault planes are due to residual tensional stress arising from crustal stretching in the main directions. The fault throws vary, in some cases, it is as much as 120m, and at times, there is no displacement such that it amounts to a fracture. Figure 6 is a structural depth map of seismic facies unit four with the location of the igneous intrusion labeled A and the graben labeled B. The orientation of main fault planes is approximately northeast – southwest and somehow zig-zag. The subordinate faults are oriented mainly in a northwest – southeast direction. The implication of this is that seismic profiles shot in a northwest – southeast direction (strike direction) will reveal more faulting systems than those shot in the northeast – southwest direction in the basin. The graben resulted from a down throw between two adjacent fault planes running approximately in the northeast – southwest direction with a distance between them ranging from 2.38km in the southwest direction to 4.5km towards the northeast direction.

Figure 7 presents schematic illustrations of the common structural trapping features in the study area. All the fault related structures have steep gradient fault planes, and believed to be initiated in deep basement rocks. The steep fault planes may not seal and can thus be multidirectional pathways for petroleum migration and hence disseminated in the formations. There is a general absence of low angle normal faults, strike – slip faults and a defined regional pattern of folds which indicate absence of an active regional compressional stress. This is a common feature of rifted basins where compressional stress and shear stress are minimal as compared to tensional stress. The consequence of a dominantly active tensional stress is crustal stretching and thinning, development of fractures / high angle normal faults, graben / rift valley, horst, magmatic intrusion and eventually reverse faults. Avbovbo *et al.*, (1986), had presented the stages of development of structural features in the Chad basin based on rifting model. They inferred that the numerous high – angle normal faults and rare reverse faults are indicative of a dominant active tensional stress in this sector of the basin that occurred in the Cretaceous. All the common structural elements in this basin terminate around the upper sequence boundary.

Interval velocities within and around the symmetrical fold / structural highs are usually very high, in the range of 4400 to 4800ms⁻¹. This suggests the following lithologies: crystalline rocks, highly compacted carbonate rocks and salt diapirs. Reflection configuration within these structural highs is mainly chaotic (Figure 4). Onlap termination pattern that is often associated with carbonate reefs / mounds and isoberg is virtually absent thus implying the absence of these features.

Fig. 7: Schematic illustration of common structural traps in Northeastern Nigeria Chad (Bornu) Basin.

Fig. 8: Logs signatures and deduced lithologic sequence of an exploratory well in Doili area of Northeastern Nigeria Chad (Bornu) Basin.

Elsewhere from these structural highs, interval velocities vary from 1600 to 3100ms⁻¹ from the earth's surface to a depth of 3387m thus implying common siliciclastics. The arched strata even though fairly distorted still exhibit some elements of abundance and continuity of reflections. Gravity survey in the Bornu basin (Cratchley, (1960), and Aina, (1988), had indicated randomly distributed intrusives that arched the Cretaceous strata into a series of folds and associated synclines. Based on time-depth conversion of seismic data, the intrusives have an average depth of 1820m from the earth's surface.

Log sequence Analysis and Evaluation of Reservoirs' Facies

A deduction of lithologic sequence from well logs indicates the following lithologies from the earth's surface to a depth of 3250m: (i) 0.0 to 100m: Clayey sand, (ii) 100 to 270m: Sandy clay, (iii) 270 to 725m: Shaly sand, (iv) 725 to 1450m: Shale, (v) 1450 to 1620m: Sandstone, (vi) 1620 to 2310m: Sandy shale and (vii) 2310 to 3200m: Sandstone interbedded with shale. Figure 8 presents the log responses and deduced lithologic sequence up to a depth of 3,250m. The log motif is mainly cylindrical with occasional bell and funnel shapes indicating relatively persistent depositional condition punctuated by episodic fluctuations of water depths that could have resulted from seasonal flooding, sediment supply and basin tectonics. Two sets of reservoirs' facies are deduced, these are sandstone and shaly sand. The cleanest sandstone reservoirs occur in a depth range of 1450 to 1600m, while the shaly sandstone reservoirs extend from a depth of 2310 to 3200m with increasing sand contents. The reservoirs' facies have relatively low porosity ranging from 0.1 to 0.25 as comparable to Niger Delta where a porosity value of about 35% has been reported in sandstone reservoirs. The formations resistivities are generally low indicating high

sand-clay ratio and consequently poor sorting, reduced porosity and permeability. Computed hydrocarbon saturation (S_h) of the cleanest sandstone reservoirs' facies within a depth range of 1450 to 1600m yielded a maximum value of 19.06% and index of oil movability of 0.68. This is considered too poor for commercial exploitation.

Re-Evaluation of Petroleum Prospect of Northeastern Nigeria Chad (Bornu) Basin

A larger part of the basin's stratigraphic succession when viewed in terms of source rock potentials consists of continental sediments. Thus of the six formations into which the stratigraphic sequence had been subdivided (Matheis, (1976) and Petters, (1981), only the Fika Shales are inferred truly marine. The Bima sandstone consists of mainly continental facies, while the Gongilia, Keri-Keri, Gombe sandstone and Chad Formations consists of facies deposited in environments ranging from estuarine, deltaic to marginal lacustrine (see Table 1), in other word, the facies that have source rock potentials are highly limited. Petters and Ekweozor, (1982), based on analysis of shale samples from southern part of the Chad basin for "Total Organic Carbon Content" that yielded a value of over 0.5% inferred that the terrigenous facies of the mature Fika shale evident from their low n-alkane ratio indicated that mainly wet gas might have been generated, while its marine facies is capable of generating liquid hydrocarbon.

The attitudes of the fault related structures in the basin when viewed in terms of structural traps make them less attractive because they are more of tensionally induced fault systems. According to Marlan (1990), extensional stress induced fault systems generally produce steep fault planes that are more likely to behave as open fractures and hence migratory pathways for hydrocarbons especially if there is no smearing of less permeable lithologies along them. Consequently, a further consideration of whether the fault planes are sealing or are permanently open fractures is imperative to ascertain precisely hydrocarbon migration pathways and entrapments in the Chad Basin. In the Niger Delta, for instance, there is smearing of clay along the fault planes of the growth faults thereby sealing them. Lateral continuity of reservoir facies across fault planes must be considered to ascertain whether the faults offset reservoir facies against sealing beds to provide traps. These are areas that need further study especially evidence from drilling of exploratory wells across fault planes and coring.

The timing of the folding phase of the Cretaceous strata with respect to hydrocarbon migration is necessary to establish whether it is pre, syn or post migration because if post-dating migration, the igneous intrusives could have caused remigration or outright degradation of hydrocarbon pools to gas, carbon or graphite. Seismic evidence indicates that folding of strata was post-depositional as there is no observable onlap termination relationship between the strata and the magmatic intrusives. Thus a consideration of the aforementioned factors indicate the level of risk that is involved in drilling exploratory wells based on structural trapping features in this sector of the Chad Basin. The major structural traps are adjudged not too ideal to prevent petroleum pools from being disseminated within the formations. Thus a detailed inventory of stratigraphic traps is necessary to complement the structural traps which probably can possess attitudes that are more favourable for petroleum accumulation.

CONCLUSION

The Bornu Basin (Northeastern Nigeria Chad Basin) possesses some favourable critical criteria for high petroleum prospect. These criteria include age of the basin, thickness of stratigraphic sequence, source rocks, reservoir rocks and structurally related traps. Structural analysis of the fault systems revealed that consequent to crustal stretching, thinning and rifting due to tensional stress directed northwest and southeast away from the main axis (Northeast-Southwest) of the basin resulted in a series of high angle normal and reverse faults, graben and horst. Randomly distributed magmatic intrusives have underthrust the Cretaceous strata forming a series of synclines and anticlines. There is a high probability of sinking dry holes in prospects with fault systems induced by tensional stress as the fault planes could be open fractures and thus unhindered conduits for petroleum migration. The magmatic intrusives could have severe effects on petroleum pools if they occurred post primary migration because they could cause degradation. Consequently, future drilling programs should be based beyond these structural features if successful hydrocarbon exploration is to be achieved in this sector of the basin.

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